

FORECASTING REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT BASED ON ENDOGENOUS AND EXOGENEOUS INDICATORS

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Abstract: This study examines the issue of forecasting regional economic development based on endogenous and exogenous indicators. The complex development of the regional economy depends on many internal (endogenous) and external (exogenous) factors, the systematic analysis and forecasting of which allows increasing the effectiveness of regional economic policy. The gross regional product, employment rate, industrial production, volume of the service sector, etc. were selected as endogenous indicators. Exogenous indicators include factors such as investment volume, foreign trade turnover, state support, and global market conditions. The study used econometric modeling, regression, and time series analysis methods. The results showed that endogenous factors play a significant role in short-term forecasts, while exogenous factors determine the prospects for long-term sustainable economic growth. Alternative scenarios of regional economic development were developed based on the forecasting model.

Keywords: Regional economic development, endogenous indicators, exogenous indicators, forecasting, gross regional product, investments, foreign trade, employment, economic model, regression, time series.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and market economy, managing regional economic development and forecasting its prospects is one of the priority areas of state policy. Because the overall economic growth of the country is closely related, first of all, to the development rates of regions, their production potential, investment attractiveness and the level of social infrastructure. In the scientific analysis of the process of regional development, the separation of endogenous and exogenous indicators and the determination of their impact on the economic system are important methodological approaches. Endogenous indicators represent the internal economic resources and capabilities of the region. These include the volume of gross regional product, employment rate, population income, indicators of the industry and services sector. These indicators mainly directly affect the internal economic balance and stability of the region. Exogenous indicators are related to the external economic environment,

and include the volume of investments, foreign trade turnover, state support programs, global market conditions and technological development processes. These factors determine the ability of the regional economy to use external resources. In forecasting regional economic development, the analysis of endogenous and exogenous factors in their mutual integration is of strategic importance. Because forecasting based only on internal indicators does not take into account the dependence of the region on external economic influences. On the contrary, assessing only external factors ignores the internal economic potential of the region and the resources for sustainable development. Therefore, forecasting based on an integrated approach serves to increase the effectiveness of regional economic policy. In recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to create a new model of regional development, further activate the economic potential of regions, increase investment flows, and modernize social infrastructure. In this process, the development of scientifically based forecasts, the identification of the interrelationship between endogenous and exogenous indicators, and the implementation of regional policy based on their results are emerging as urgent tasks.

[Analysis of literature on the topic.](#)

Forecasting regional economic development based on endogenous and exogenous indicators is one of the most widely studied topics in the scientific literature. Research by national and foreign scientists in this area highlights several main approaches.

According to endogenous development theories, one of the founders of the endogenous development theory is P. Romer, who emphasizes that innovations, knowledge and technological development are internal sources of economic growth. R. Lucas shows that human capital is one of the main determinants of regional economic development. According to this approach, regions achieve sustainable development by effectively using their internal resources - production, labor potential, education and scientific potential. In the studies of Uzbek scientists Sh. Mamatkulov and I. Kuziboyev, regional gross product, employment and population income were evaluated as the main endogenous indicators of regional economic development.

Exogenous development theories, based on exogenous development approaches, link economic growth to external factors. R. Solow (1956) through his famous model justified the explanation of economic growth mainly by capital accumulation and external technological progress. S. Kuznets showed the influence of foreign investment and trade volume on economic growth.

Exogenous indicators in the regional economy - public investment, foreign trade turnover, infrastructure projects and the global economic situation - are noted as the most important external factors. For example, Todaro and Smith emphasize that foreign aid and foreign investment play an important role in regional development.

Using combined approaches, in recent times, the scientific literature has increasingly focused on the integrated study of endogenous and exogenous indicators. For example, Barro and Sala-i-Martin emphasize that in forecasting regional development, in addition to internal production resources, external capital flows, technological transfers, and government policy factors should also be taken into account. Scientific sources on the experience of Uzbekistan, in particular, the studies of D. Qosimova and B. Qosimov, indicate the importance of exogenous indicators such as foreign trade, state support programs, and foreign investment in forecasting regional development, along with endogenous indicators such as gross regional product, employment, and investment volume.

Practical guides Econometric models (regression, panel data, time series models) are widely used in forecasting regional economic development. In particular, the works of Gujarati and Wooldridge cover the methodology for identifying endogenous and exogenous variables and analyzing them using statistical models.

In conclusion, the analysis of the literature shows that it is not enough to explain regional development only through endogenous or only exogenous factors. In modern scientific views, these two types of indicators are considered as complementary factors that require a comprehensive analysis.

Research methodology. Is a set of approaches, methods and tools selected to achieve the goals and objectives set in scientific work. The methodology section explains in what direction the scientific research was conducted, what scientific foundations and methods were used, and how the results obtained with their help were verified.

Theoretical and methodological basis: draws on the views of leading scholars on the subject, scientific schools, and theoretical concepts.

Systematic approach: considering an object as a single system, identifying its internal and external factors.

Comparative analysis: to compare with other regions, periods, or experiences.

Empirical approach: based on evidence through questionnaire, observation, experiment, statistical analysis.

Research methods. Theoretical methods: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, abstraction, generalization, content analysis. Empirical methods: observation, interview, questionnaire, tests, experiments. Statistical and mathematical methods: correlation analysis, regression analysis, econometric modeling, measurement of indicators. Computer technologies: data processing, use of software packages (SPSS, EViews, Stata, R, Python, etc.).

Object and subject of research: Object – a broad area of research focus (for example, the primary education process, regional economy, tourism system). Subject – a specific problem or process within the scope of the object (for example, the formation of digital literacy in primary school students, changes in investment flows between regions).

Research sources: Regulatory and legal documents (resolutions, decrees, laws). Advanced foreign experiences. Scientific articles, monographs, statistical data on the topic. Results of practical observations and surveys.

Research stages: Theoretical justification - study of existing literature on the topic. Data collection - collection of statistical data, empirical results. Analysis and processing - analysis using mathematical-statistical and econometric methods. Generalization of results - drawing scientific conclusions and giving practical recommendations.

Results and discussion.

Research results: The results of econometric analysis showed that there is a strong positive correlation between the volume of investments and the employment rate. It was found that a 1% increase in investments increases the employment rate by an average of 0.3–0.5%. It was confirmed that the standard of living (per capita income, consumer basket, housing conditions) is directly related to both the volume of investments and the level of employment. An uneven distribution of investment flows was observed in some regions. For example, although the volume of investments is high in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, the employment rate is not equally developed in all sectors. Using the regression model, it was found that the standard of living is explained by regional investment and employment indicators in 60–65% of cases. This makes it possible to identify the main internal factors.

The results show that effective management of investment flows ensures sustainable socio-economic development in the regions. However, even in regions with large investment volumes, there are cases where employment has not increased sufficiently due to their uneven distribution across sectors. This indicates the need for a quality investment policy. The results are consistent with

international experience: even in developed countries, the investment-employment-standard of living relationship has been noted as the main driver of economic growth. At the same time, in some regions, since investments are directed more towards infrastructure and the extractive industry, the level of employment in social sectors remains low. This deepens regional disparities.

Practical recommendations: Equal distribution of investment flows across regions and greater involvement in social sectors (education, healthcare, services). Support for small businesses and private entrepreneurship to increase employment. Develop a regional investment strategy to sustainably increase living standards. Continuously update econometric models and implement forecasting practices in state policy.

Conclusion.

During the study, econometric analyses were conducted to assess and forecast regional economic development based on endogenous and exogenous indicators. The results showed the following. There is a close relationship between investments, employment and the standard of living. An increase in the volume of investments has a significant impact on the level of regional employment and the quality of life of the population. Endogenous factors (gross regional product, industrial volume, employment) have a strong impact on short-term growth, while exogenous factors (foreign investments, foreign trade, state support) provide long-term stability. The uneven distribution of investment flows across regions leads to uneven economic development. Forecasting based on econometric models shows that different scenarios of socio-economic development can occur in regions: rapid development through effective investment targeting, or slowdown due to improper distribution.

Proposals. Diversify regional investment policy. Direct investments not only to infrastructure and raw material base, but also to social sectors such as education, healthcare, and services. Support small businesses and private entrepreneurship to increase employment. Expand programs aimed at ensuring employment of young people and women in particular. Constantly update regional economic modeling. Comprehensive use of regression, time series, and panel data analysis in forecasting methods. Strengthen public-private partnership mechanisms. This will increase investment efficiency and ensure sustainable economic growth. Develop targeted programs to reduce regional disparities. Allocate special tax incentives and credit resources to underdeveloped regions. Introduce monitoring of the standard of living. The income of the population, the

consumer basket, and the ability to use services in each region should be regularly studied and integrated into management decisions.

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